

Autocratic Leadership Style in Higher Education Institutions: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

An autocratic leader is one who centralizes authority and decision-making. In this leadership model, there is a strong focus on achieving results, with less consideration given to the well-being or input of team members. It operates under the assumption that individuals are inherently unmotivated, unreliable, and lack responsibility. Consequently, core functions such as planning, organizing, controlling, and decision-making are concentrated in the leader, with minimal participation or influence from subordinates. Autocratic leadership, characterized by centralized control, rigid decision-making, and limited participation from subordinates, can be found in various educational settings despite the collaborative nature of academia. This paper reviews the current literature on autocratic leadership, examining both the potential benefits, such as swift decision-making and a clear chain of command, as well as the drawbacks, including stifled innovation and reduced staff morale. This study explores the implications and characteristics of autocratic leadership in higher education institutions via bibliometric reviews of scientific publications, such as journals and articles. In all, 61 influential studies published between 2012 and 2024 were critically conducted via VOSviewer version 1.6.20 to identify relevant literature. The findings highlight the challenges this leadership style poses in academic environments, where autonomy and intellectual freedom are traditionally valued. Through a case analysis of specific higher education institutions, the study identifies situations where autocratic leadership may be effective and where it could hinder institutional growth. The paper concludes by offering recommendations for balancing authority with collaboration to foster a healthier academic environment.

Keywords: *Autocratic leadership, Higher education, Leadership effectiveness.*

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Introduction

Higher education faces numerous challenges in the 21st century, including economic uncertainty, accountability, and globalization (Richardson et al., 2017). Leaders must navigate a rapidly changing landscape characterized by technological advancements and shifting workforce needs (Delener, 2013; Khahro & Javed, 2022). Effective leadership is crucial for institutional success, requiring a paradigm shift toward visionary and strategic management (Olcott et al., 2023). Leadership in higher education has been extensively studied, with research focusing on various leadership styles and their impacts. Bibliometric analyses have revealed increasing interest in leadership models such as distributed, instructional, teacher, and transformational leadership (Esen et al., 2020). Recent studies indicate a preference for democratic-transformational, democratic, and transactional leadership styles among faculty and staff (Mews, 2019). Recent bibliometric reviews have examined leadership research in higher education, revealing a scarcity of studies and limited growth over the past two decades. However, leadership models such as distributed, instructional, teacher, and transformational leadership have gained attention (Esen et al., 2020). The paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 offers a concise literature review. Section 3 details the research methodology. Section 4 presents the study's findings. Section 5 provides a comprehensive discussion and concludes with the implications of the research.

Literature Review

What is Autocratic Leadership?

Autocratic leadership is characterized by centralized authority and limited subordinate participation in decision-making. This style is often associated with postcolonial African states and can lead to professional brutality (Maseti & Gumede, 2011). In academic libraries, autocratic leadership tends to develop dependent, uncreative subordinates and negatively impacts employee performance and job satisfaction (Chukwusa, 2018; Kalu & Okpokwasili, 2018; Akor, 2014). However, it may be valuable in situations requiring quick, decisive action (Kalu & Okpokwasili, 2018). Autocratic leadership is less effective in wealthier countries with demanding climates but more effective in poorer countries with demanding climates (Vliert, 2006). It can also predict passive-aggressive behaviors in the workplace (Johnson & Klee, 2007). While autocratic leadership may be useful in the short term, democratic and participative styles are generally more beneficial for long-term employee performance (Iqbal et al., 2015). Training leaders in academic leadership is recommended to improve quality assurance in higher education institutions (Mboya et al., 2018).

What are the Key Elements of Autocratic Leadership?

Autocratic leadership, characterized by centralized decision-making and limited employee input, has both advantages and drawbacks. While it can enable quick decision-making in crisis situations (Kalu Dolly C & Okpokwasili Nonyelum P., 2018), it often leads to reduced employee creativity, job dissatisfaction, and lower productivity (Chukwusa, 2018; Kalu Dolly C & Okpokwasili Nonyelum P., 2018). Autocratic leadership is more prevalent in postcolonial African states (Maseti & Gumede, 2011) and poorer countries with demanding climates (Vliert, 2006). It can be effective in religious institutions such as Islamic boarding schools (Arif et al., 2021). However, democratic and participative leadership styles generally result in greater job satisfaction and employee performance (Bhatti et al., 2012; Iqbal et al., 2015). Interestingly, individuals experiencing self-uncertainty tend to show greater support for autocratic leaders, which is mediated by perceived group prototypicality (Rast et al., 2013). Overall, while autocratic leadership may be useful in specific contexts, it is generally considered less effective than more inclusive leadership styles.

Achievements of Autocratic Leadership

Research on leadership styles reveals mixed effects on employee performance and organizational success. Autocratic leadership has been found to negatively impact employee productivity, job satisfaction, and morale in academic libraries (Kalu & Okpokwasili, 2018; Chukwusa, 2018). It can lead to dependent and uncreative subordinates (Kalu & Okpokwasili, 2018) and hinder problem solving (Chukwusa, 2018). However, autocratic leadership may be valuable in situations requiring quick decision-making (Kalu & Okpokwasili, 2018). In contrast, democratic leadership styles generally have positive effects on employee performance and satisfaction (Setiawan et al., 2021; Ahmad et al., 2014; Chua et al., 2018). A meta-analysis revealed no overall correlation between leadership style and productivity, but democratic leadership correlated positively with member satisfaction (Gastil, 1994). In academic institutions, autocratic leadership has shown positive correlations with quality assurance (Mboya et al., 2018). Recent research in Iraqi universities confirms that democratic leadership positively impacts job satisfaction, whereas autocratic leadership negatively affects it (Saadi et al., 2023).

Methodology

Bibliometric analysis is a quantitative method used to examine scientific publications and track research trends. It involves analyzing various aspects, such as publication patterns, influential authors, institutions, and keywords (Kumari & Lenka, 2023; Hyland & Jiang, 2023). This approach has gained popularity across diverse fields, including disability inclusion, English teaching materials, and big data research (Kumari & Lenka, 2023; Wang & Ping, 2023; Islam & Hu, 2023). Bibliometric studies often utilize specialized software such as Biblioshiny and Bibliometric to process and visualize data from databases such as the Web of Science (Kumari & Lenka, 2023; Mir & Rathinam, 2023). These analyses can reveal research trends, collaboration patterns, and impactful publications, providing valuable insights for researchers and policymakers (Shushanyan & Ohanyan, 2021; Lazarides et al., 2023).

The secondary data for this study were extracted from the Scopus database, a comprehensive repository encompassing a wide spectrum of academic disciplines. The dataset included abstracts and citation information derived from journals, conference proceedings, and patents. A bibliometric analysis of 61 influential studies published between 2012 and 2024 was conducted via VOSviewer version 1.6.20 to identify relevant literature.

Results

The VOS viewer is known for networks and often includes clustering algorithms that group related entities. This process allows for the identification of patterns and trends in the dataset.

Figure 1. Documents by Year

This chart reflects a fluctuating pattern in publication output, with a steady rise leading to a peak from 2021--2022, followed by a decline. The reasons for these trends could be explored further by examining potential factors such as research funding, collaboration, or external events such as the COVID-19 pandemic that might have influenced the surge in publications from 2021--2022 and the subsequent decline.

Figure 2. Document by Subject Area

This pie chart shows a breakdown of academic publications filtered by subject area, ranked by the number of results in each category. Here's how to interpret the figure:

The social sciences led with the greatest number of publications (31 results), suggesting that this field has the most studies or articles related to the topic being researched.

Medicine follows with 10 results, indicating significant but less research attention than social sciences do.

The multidisciplinary approach is next, with 9 results, reflecting research that spans multiple subject areas.

Other categories, such as psychology, arts and humanities, health professions, environmental science, computer science, business, management, and accounting, all have smaller numbers (ranging from 6--3 results), indicating moderate research interest in these fields.

Finally, Energy and Economics, Econometrics, and Finance have the fewest publications, with 2 results each.

The figure highlights which academic fields have contributed more research on the given topic, helping to identify the primary disciplines engaged in this area. The dominance of the social sciences suggests that this field plays a critical role in studying the subject matter.

Figure 3. Network Visualization of Research Trends

The image represents different themes related to leadership, with central focus areas such as human behavior, government, and leadership styles (authoritarian, democratic). Each cluster indicates a distinct aspect or perspective on leadership, with significant relationships between them.

Figure 4. Overlay Visualization of Research Trends

This network visualization shows how various terms related to leadership have been discussed over time, from 2018--2020. Early studies (blue) focused more on general leadership and governmental roles, whereas later studies (green and yellow) began exploring more specific leadership styles, particularly authoritarian and democratic leadership. Additionally, motivation, gender roles, and the human aspect of leadership became prominent topics later in the timeline.

Table 1. Top 20 Citations of the First Author Background from 2012-2024

Authors	Affiliations	Country	Cited by
Natter K.	University of Amsterdam	Netherlands	85
Jones B.D.	University of Texas at Austin	United States	27
Reta Y.	Debire Berhan University	Ethiopia	27
Jungherr A.	University of Bamberg	Germany	26
Thompson A.E.	Negaunee Integrative Research Center	United States	26
Kars M.	Mersin University	Turkey	24
Nai A.	University of Amsterdam	Turkey	23
Guptill M.	Loma Linda University	United States	23
Matthews L.J.	University of Auckland	Germany	22
Balashov V.S.	Rutgers School of Business-Camden	United States	18
Gregorio L.E.	University of Connecticut	United States	17
Nxumalo N.	University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg	South Africa	15
Sari I.	Sakarya Üniversitesi Spor Bilimleri Fakültesi	Turkey	12
Jiménez M.	Universidad Internacional de La Rioja	Spain	12
Maerz S.F.	Bard College Berlin	Germany	11
Jin H.	Hong Kong Baptist University	Hongkong	10
Lees-Marshment J.	School of Social Sciences	New Zealand	10
Rosales A.	University of New Brunswick	Canada	9
Rawat S.R.	Symbiosis International University	India	9
Thon R.A.	Universidade Estadual de Maringá	Brazil	9

The table highlights the global reach of research output, with authors from diverse institutions and countries being recognized for their work on the basis of citation counts. Nater, K. from the Netherlands stands out with the highest citation count, whereas other notable contributions come from institutions in the United States, Turkey, and Germany.

Table 2. Number of Papers by the top 10 Countries for the 2012-2024 Period

Country	Number of papers	Percentage (%)
United States	16	26.22
Brazil	8	13.11
Germany	8	13.11
United Kingdom	8	13.11
Turkey	4	6.55
Netherlands	3	4.91
Ukraine	2	3.27
Sweden	2	3.27
South Africa	2	3.27
Slovakia	2	3.27

The table shows a strong contribution from developed countries, with the United States leading the chart. European countries, such as Germany, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, and Sweden, also make significant contributions, whereas Brazil stands out as a key contributor from Latin America. Some emerging economies, such as Turkey and South Africa, have moderate representation, indicating global diversity in research output over the 2012--2024 period.

Discussion and Conclusion

Leadership Styles

Research on autocratic and democratic leadership styles reveals complex relationships with organizational outcomes. Democratic leadership generally correlates positively with member satisfaction (Gastil, 1994) and job satisfaction (Bhatti et al., 2012), whereas autocratic leadership can increase counterproductive behaviors and work alienation (Erdem, 2021). However, the effectiveness of each style may depend on context. In emergency situations, autocratic leadership can build trust during action phases, whereas democratic leadership is more effective in transition phases (Rosing et al., 2022). Leadership style impacts may also vary on the basis of climate and wealth, with autocratic leadership potentially more effective in poorer countries with demanding climates (Vliert, 2006). Personality traits can predict leadership style (Rosenfeld & Plax, 1975), and communication behaviors differ between autocratic and democratic leaders (Sargent & Miller, 1971). Despite its negative connotations, autocratic leadership remains prevalent in some postcolonial African states (Maseti & Gumede, 2011).

Autocratic Leadership Dynamics

Autocratic leadership, characterized by centralized authority and limited employee input, remains prevalent in various contexts despite being considered outdated (Maseti & Gumede, 2011). While it can enhance operational efficiency, autocratic leadership often undermines trust, creativity, and problem solving in organizations (Chukwusa, 2018; Modise, 2024). Its effectiveness varies across cultures, with poorer countries in demanding climates showing more positive outcomes (Van de Vliert, 2006). Autocratic leadership is particularly common in postcolonial African states and some corporate sectors (Maseti & Gumede, 2011; Chishty-Mujahid, 2016). However, it can negatively impact job performance and employee morale in academic settings (Akor, 2014). Interestingly, individuals experiencing self-uncertainty tend to show greater support for autocratic leaders, which is mediated by perceived group prototypicality (Rast et al., 2013). Overall, while autocratic leadership may offer some benefits in specific contexts, its drawbacks often outweigh its advantages, particularly in modern, complex organizational environments (Modise, 2024).

Democratic Leadership Dynamics

Democratic leadership is a participatory style that encourages collaboration, free exchange of ideas, and shared decision-making (Woods, 2021). It is characterized by power sharing, transformative dialog, and the cultivation of holistic learning and relational well-being (Woods, 2020). Democratic leaders distribute responsibility, empower group members, and aid in decision-making processes (Gastil, 1994). Key characteristics include sacrifice, courage, symbolism, citizen participation, and vision (Choi, 2007). Democratic leadership is distinct from distributed leadership, as it emphasizes decisional and ethical rationality (Woods, 2004). It requires leaders to navigate between public cynicism and idealism (Kane & Patapan, 2012) and recruit citizens as partners in shared political activity (Beerbohm, 2015). While challenging to implement, democratic leadership is considered essential for the strength and stability of democracies (Kane & Patapan, 2012).

The Relationship between Motivation and Autocratic Leadership

Research on leadership styles and employee motivation reveals complex relationships. Autocratic leadership generally has a negative or insignificant effect on motivation (Fiaz et al., 2017; Al Altheeb, 2020), although one study reported that it positively influences motivation in a military context (Warsono et al., 2019). Democratic and participative leadership styles tend to have positive effects on motivation and coach-athlete relationships (Jin et al., 2022; Syed Ahmad & Parnabas, 2019). Transformational leadership is associated with increased employee commitment and motivation (Naile & Selesho, 2014; Vasileva & Datta, 2021). Charismatic leadership also has a positive influence on motivation (Khuong & Hoang, 2015). The effectiveness of leadership styles may vary depending on the organizational context and culture. For instance, paternalistic leadership was found to be effective in Saudi Arabia (Al Altheeb, 2020). Overall, these studies suggest that democratic, participative, and transformational leadership styles are generally more effective in motivating employees across various sectors and cultures.

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